

An antimatter space production station for crewed interstellar travel

TECHNICAL NOTE

Antimatter propulsion has been considered as probably the most promising method of interstellar propulsion. It has been proposed that beamed cored antimatter propulsion could actually reach 69% the speed of light (Keane et al, 2012). Such speed would allow humanity to reach the closest potentially habitable exoplanet in slightly over 6 years.

There are several techniques to produce antimatter. One of them is pair production through the use of high energy lasers. The process basically consists in shooting a laser into a cloud of electrons, which produces a series of gamma rays. When these rays collide with each other, they produce pairs of electrons and positrons, the latter of which can be extracted and stored. So far, antimatter has been stored during a total of 405 days (Sellner et al, 2017). The main problem is that high energy lasers can only run during very short periods of time, usually in the femtosecond order.

For this reason, here we propose to use a combination of a mirror system and a solar-pumped laser in order to produce the quantities of antimatter needed for antimatter propulsion. Unlike electrical lasers, solar pumped-lasers can run continuously. Several models using Fresnel lenses have been proposed by other authors, but the solar radiation on

Earth is extremely low: only 1,380 watts per squared meter. For this reason, we alternatively propose the construction of a two mirror-system that would be sent close to the Sun in order to collect a sufficient amount of light. More specifically, a 100-meter mirror system would be sent as close as 0.01 AU units from the Sun. An antimatter production station, which could be located in the Lagrange point L1, would receive the collected light and produce antimatter with a solar-pumped laser. Considering a typical solar-pumped laser efficiency of 10%, the laser would have an energy of around 1.34E+10 watts per second, and the amount of antimatter produced in one year would be half of the following:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= m \cdot c^2 \\ m &= \frac{E}{c^2} \\ &= \frac{4.2e+17}{300,000,000^2} \\ &= 4.7 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

Another important aspect that should be considered is the production of electrons, which are needed to produce gamma rays when they collide with photons. NASA's nuclear fission reactor Kilopower could be the best option to power an electron beam generator. This reactor is able to produce 10 KW of power continuously during 15 years.